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SUB-LETHAL EFFECTS OF TITANIUM DIOXIDE (TiO₂) PM₁
ON HONEY BEE GUT MICROBIOTA

*Effetti sub-letali del biossido di titanio (TiO₂, PM₁)
sul microbiota intestinale dell'ape da miele*

Apis mellifera Linnaeus, 1758, is an important provider of ecosystem services, and during flight and foraging behaviour is exposed to environmental pollutants including airborne particulate matter (PM) (NEGRI *et al.*, 2015; PAPA *et al.*, 2020). While exposure to insecticides, antibiotics, and herbicides may compromise bees gut microbial community, no data are available on the impacts of PM on the bee microbiota.

This research investigates the effects of acute and chronic oral administration of submicrometric PM ultrapure Titanium dioxide (TiO₂ rutile) on honey bee gut microbiota. The submicrometric TiO₂ is widely used as a filler and whitening agent in a range of manufactured objects, and ultrapure TiO₂ is also a common food additive, albeit classified by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) as a possible human carcinogen in Group 2B. The particle used was PM₁; ranging from 800 to 200 nm as characterized by SEM-EDX analysis. Newly eclosed worker bees were fed ad libitum with two different concentrations of TiO₂ (100 ng/μL and 10 ng/μL) in sucrose solution. The bees were orally exposed to the selected doses of TiO₂ in an acute (single treatment, sampling at 24h) and a chronic application (treatments repeated every 24h, sampling at 96h). The presence of TiO₂ in the haemolymph and gut of chronic bees was investigated by SEM-EDX. The DNA was extracted from gut samples collected for microbiological analyses and the V3-V4 region of the bacterial 16S rRNA gene was amplified by PCR. In both assays, we obtained no mortality for the entire trials. TiO₂ dust was

characterised by SEM/EDX, showing no contaminants or coatings. We did not record TiO₂ PM in the haemolymph. SEM observation performed on chronic and control gut highlighted the presence of K₂SO₄ salts. In the rectum of treated bees, TiO₂ was found both associated and not associated with K₂SO₄ crystals.

Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) showed a clear distinction in bacterial community structure between the chronic and the acute experiments, and in the chronic experiments among controls and treated bees.

We found dose-dependent increase in diversity, while the opposite was found for the neonicotinoid insecticide Thiacloprid (LIU *et al.*, 2020), polystyrene particles at µm levels (WANG *et al.*, 2021), and antibiotics (RAYMANN, SHAFFER & MORAN, 2017). Importantly, in our study sub-lethal doses were tested and no mortality registered, possibly due to the increase in diversity of the microbiota in response to the sub-lethal stressors.

In the acute test, the abundance of only one species, *L. kimbladii*, was significantly reduced by the highest dose of TiO₂ applied. This species has been recently proposed as a possible probiotic (MÄRTENSSON *et al.*, 2016; DUONG *et al.*, 2020). Interestingly, *L. kimbladii* was instead found at higher abundances in the bees 96 h from the chronic exposure. This change may point to an adaptation in time of the microbial community, with a probiotic species becoming more abundant to counteract the chronic effects of a chemical stressor (ZHU *et al.*, 2020).

REFERENCES

- DUONG B.T.T., LIEN N.T.K., THU H.T., HOA N.T., LANH P.T., YUN B-R., YOO M-S., CHO Y.S. & VAN QUYEN D., 2020. Investigation of the gut microbiome of *Apis cerana* honeybees from Vietnam. *Biotechnology Letters*, 42: 2309–2317.
- LIU Y.J., QIAO N.H., DIAO Q.Y., JING Z., VUKANTI R, DAI P.L. & GE Y., 2020. Thiacloprid exposure perturbs the gut microbiota and reduces the survival status in honeybees. *J. Hazardous Materials*, 389:121818.
- MÄRTENSSON A., GREIFF L., LAMEI S.S., LINDSTEDT M., OLOFSSON T.C., VASQUEZ A. & CERVIN A., 2016. Effects of a honeybee lactic acid bacterial microbiome on human nasal symptoms, commensals, and biomarkers. *Int. Forum Allergy & Rhinology*, 6:956–963.
- NEGRI I., MAVRIS C., DI PRISCO G., CAPRIO E. & PELLECCIA M., 2015. Honey bees (*Apis mellifera*, L.) as active samplers of airborne particulate matter. *PLoS ONE* 10:1–22.
- PAPA G., CAPITANI G., CAPRI E., PELLECCIA M. & NEGRI I., 2020. Vehicle-derived ultrafine particulate contaminating bees and bee products. *Science of The Total Environment*: 141700. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141700.
- RAYMANN K., SHAFFER Z. & MORAN N.A., 2017. Antibiotic exposure perturbs the gut microbiota and elevates mortality in honeybees. *PLoS Biology* 15:1–22.
- WANG K., LI J., ZHAO L., MU X., WANG C., WANG M., XUE X., QI S. & WU L., 2021. Gut microbiota protects honey bees (*Apis mellifera* L.) against polystyrene microplastics exposure risks. *J. Hazardous Materials*, 402:123828. DOI: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.123828.

ZHU L., QI S., XUE X., NIU X. & WU L., 2020. Nitenpyram disturbs gut microbiota and influences metabolic homeostasis and immunity in honey bee (*Apis mellifera* L.). *Environ. Poll.*, 258:113671; DOI: 10.1016/j.envpol.2019.113671.

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